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Research on the Influence of Self-Efficacy, Training Motivation, and Training Outcomes on the Employment Intentions of Unemployed Youth in Taiwan Government Vocational Training Programs

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Abstract

This study originates from the observation of youth unemployment in Taiwan society and explores whether unemployed youth can successfully transition to the workplace through participation in Taiwan government vocational training. It examines the effects of individual self-efficacy, training motivation, and training effectiveness on employment intentions. The research method utilized a questionnaire survey, with a total of 121 questionnaires collected. SmartPLS and SPSS were used as statistical analysis software to conduct descriptive statistics, reliability and validity analysis, and regression analysis. The empirical results are as follows: self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on training effectiveness; a significant positive impact between self-efficacy and employment intentions; training motivation has a significant positive impact on training effectiveness; training motivation does not have a significant impact on employment intentions; and training effectiveness has a significant positive impact on employment intentions. In addition to the five hypotheses within the research framework, this study also conducted independent sample T-tests, one-way ANOVA, mediation effects, and moderation effects analyses, and got several empirical results as follows: training effectiveness partially mediates the impact of self-efficacy on employment intentions; males generally have higher self-efficacy than females; trainees who attempted to seek employment before training generally have higher employment intentions than those who did not; and trainees aged 25-29 generally have higher employment intentions than those aged 15-19.

Keywords: Vocational Training, Self-Efficacy, Training Motivation, Training Effectiveness, Employment Intentions

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Unemployment affects individuals in multiple ways. Beyond the loss of income and departure from a structured lifestyle, it significantly impacts psychological well-being, causing feelings of frustration, anxiety, depression, and decreased self-confidence (Vega, 2023). When facing unemployment, the consequences extend beyond the

individual to affect family and societal levels. Studies indicate that unemployment leads to higher divorce rates and issues in child-rearing. The negative impacts of unemployment do not cease once a new job is found; rather, they persist for up to two years (Jin, Shah, & Svoboda, 1995). One research demonstrated that, which tracked 756 job seekers within 13 weeks of unemployment, 71% reported that the negative effects of their initial unemployment experience continued to affect them (Marinescu, Skandalis, & Zhao, 2020).

Maintaining a positive attitude during unemployment influences the success rate of future job searches, a concept known as positive psychological capital. This includes hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism. Self-efficacy, in particular, has a significant positive correlation with individual job performance, highlighting the importance of studying self-efficacy among the unemployed (Judge, Jackson, Shaw, Scott, & Rich, 2007). To escape unemployment, individuals typically take several actions, such as job matching, updating resumes, and enhancing their skills. Unemployment drives the motivation to improve one's capabilities, leading many to participate in vocational training courses with the expectation that these courses will help them secure employment. Thus, understanding the motivation for training and the effectiveness of these training programs is crucial.

1.2 Explore Importance of the Problem

According to Taiwanese government statistics, the unemployment rate is highest among three age groups: 15-19 years, 20-24 years, and 25-29 years, ranging from 6% to 15% (Judge et al., 2007). These numbers indicate that the unemployment issue is significantly more severe among the youth compared to the middle-aged population. To encourage youth employment, the Taiwanese government offers employment incentives and vocational training program, called "The First Industrial Talents." Given that participating in vocational training courses is more beneficial for the overall career development of young people, this study focuses on government-provided vocational training. It investigates the effects of self-efficacy, training motivation, and training effectiveness on the employment intentions of unemployed youth participating in this vocational training program. Therefore, three research goals are demonstrated in this study:

1. Investigate whether vocational training can effectively help unemployed youth secure employment.
2. Examine how different characteristics of trainees' influence training effectiveness and future employment outcomes.
3. Provide guidelines for government training institutions to select suitable youth trainees.

1.3 Describe Relevant Scholarship

The term "self-efficacy" was first introduced within the framework of social learning theory (Rumjaun & Narod, 2020). Social learning theory posits that an individual's behavior is primarily influenced by the interplay between social environment, personal cognition, and personal behavior. An individual's expectations of efficacy primarily derive from mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological and emotional states. Self-efficacy represents an individual's belief in their capability to accomplish a specific task, typically expressed through phrases like "I believe I can" or "I am confident." It reflects a psychological assessment of one's ability to perform a particular behavior. Individuals with higher self-efficacy tend to set more challenging goals for themselves, believing in their capacity to apply learning outcomes and competencies to their work. They persist in their efforts to enhance job performance (Rumjaun & Narod, 2020; Simosi, 2012). Before making career choices, job seekers often engage in self-assessment to select tasks they can competently perform, while avoiding those beyond their abilities. Job seekers with high self-efficacy are more likely to accept challenging tasks, leading to a broader range of job options (Saks, Zikic, & Koen, 2015). Conversely, if job seekers experience repeated failures, their self-efficacy diminishes, the level of task challenge they can accept decreases, and their job options narrow, leading to a vicious cycle of unsuccessful job searching. To counteract the decline in self-efficacy caused by "mastery experiences," job seekers need to boost their self-efficacy through other factors. For example, observing

others successfully finding jobs can foster belief in their own potential success based on “vicarious experiences.” Positive reinforcement and encouragement from others can affirm the job seeker's efforts and current skills, thus enhancing self-efficacy through “verbal persuasion” (Hagen, Gutkin, Wilson, & Oats, 1998). Avoiding mention of past failures is crucial. Additionally, maintaining a structured schedule and rhythm, preserving mental and physical well-being, and experiencing “physiological arousal” can help job seekers feel good about their current state, thereby sustaining high self-efficacy (O’Leary, 1992).

Training motivation refers to the reasons why participants enroll in educational training programs (O’Leary, 1992). By understanding their motivation, we can discern what participants hope to gain from the courses. Tharenou (2001) indicated that training motivation arises from the value expected by the trainees, which, under the influence of learning motivation, generates the willingness to participate in training. Beier and Kanfer (2009) also suggested that training motivation involves the willingness and expectations of trainees to engage in training and development before the course, with the goal of acquiring work-related knowledge and skills. Boshier (1971) proposed congruence model theory for adult learning, stating that the motivation for adults to engage in further education is determined by the degree of interaction between external social factors and internal self-factors. When this balance is disrupted, the drive to restore it leads to the emergence of learning motivation. Boshier categorizes learning motivation into two types: growth motivation and deficiency motivation. Deci and Ryan (1985) introduced the self-determination theory, which posits that an individual’s motivation can be categorized into extrinsic and intrinsic motivation based on the level of self-determination. Ilie (2019) explored the impact of motivation and satisfaction on training effectiveness, using the government-subsidized vocational program as an example. Ilie (2019) also divided training motivation into three types: learning motivation, intrinsic goals, and external expectations. Given that adults have the autonomy to decide whether to participate and which course to enroll in, the training motivation of each individual varies. Therefore, understanding the types of training motivation and the differences in training effectiveness they bring is crucial. Everyone has different learning goals. Such individual learning goals are reflected in their training motivation.

Training effectiveness encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that employees acquire from educational training, signifying the performance outcomes produced by both employees and the organization through the training process (Dessler, Cole, & Chhinzer, 2015). Training effectiveness is reflected in the participants’ satisfaction with various aspects of the training process and the extent to which they enhance their self-capabilities and apply them in the workplace (McCombs, 2012). Training effectiveness represents the extent of learning and acquisition by participants upon the completion of educational training courses. It is a key indicator of whether the costs incurred for the training have yielded corresponding results. The evaluation models for training effectiveness are diverse, including Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Evaluation Model, the CIPP Evaluation Model, Brinkerhoff's Six-Stage Evaluation Model, Bushnell's IPO Model, Holton's HRD Evaluation and Measurement Model, and Phillips' ROI Model. From research study, it can say that the models for evaluating training effectiveness are varied, each with its own methods and logic (Passmore & Velez, 2012; Passmore & Velez, 2014; Reio Jr, Rocco, Smith, & Chang, 2017). Since this study involves surveying the trainees, there is limited information about the resources, facilities, and other investments made by the training organization. Given that many contemporary training evaluation models are extensions and applications of Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Evaluation Model, this study primarily adopts Kirkpatrick's model as the sub-dimension framework for designing the questionnaire on training effectiveness.

Intention is not merely an expression of attitude or cognition; it also represents the degree of willingness to take action. Vallerand, Deshaies, Cuerrier, Pelletier, and Mongeau (1992) defined intention as the subjective inclination of an individual to engage in a specific behavior. Intention signifies a willingness to perform an action or initiate a behavior, providing the motivation to move towards desired goals (Ajzen, 1985). Regardless of educational background, everyone must face their first job search. From choosing schools and majors in the past to selecting companies and careers now, students need references and guidelines to help them find the right answers for themselves. Cullen, Edwards, Casper, and Gue (2014) suggested that employment intention reflects an individual's inclination to seek satisfaction and adaptability in a job, which relates to personal traits and environmental factors.

Douglas and Shepherd (2002) also pointed out that employment intention refers to an individual's career choice based on their abilities, interests, work values, and future career perceptions, representing their intent to achieve future employment goals. The variations and reasons for differences in employment intentions arise from the interplay of factors such as family background, personal characteristics, work values, and social interaction opportunities (Douglas & Shepherd, 2002). Chen, Shen, and Gosling (2021) studied the relationships between workplace competencies, student internship satisfaction, and future employment intentions, surveying students who completed internships in the tourism and leisure industry. The findings showed that students had a high willingness to try jobs in the tourism and leisure sector, scoring an average of 3.93, the highest among the categories. However, Chen et al. (2021) also inferred that the high employment intention among students might be due to their understanding of the industry after more than two years of related coursework. If they lack clear ideas about their future career direction, they are more likely to consider their field of study as a priority for future employment. Conversely, some students experience conflicting feelings after external internships, which can negatively impact their employment intentions.

1.4 State Hypotheses and Their Correspondence to Research Design

Switzer, Nagy, and Mullins (2005) pointed out that self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on training transfer effectiveness. Na-Nan and Sanamthong (2020) also demonstrated that employees' self-efficacy significantly influences training effectiveness. Based on the above literature, this study hypothesizes that self-efficacy is positively related to educational training effectiveness, leading to the first hypothesis: unemployed youth with high self-efficacy will have higher training effectiveness after participating in vocational training.

H1: Self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on educational training effectiveness

Hackett and Betz (1981) found that self-efficacy's predictive value is highly related to individuals' workplace behavior. It can be further inferred that the self-efficacy of unemployed youth influences their level of engagement in employment intentions, affecting their job choices. A research about the impact of tourism and hospitality students' internships on their future employment, found that students with high self-efficacy strive to overcome difficulties during internships and are willing to pursue related industries in the future (Tsai, Hsu, & Yang, 2017). Based on the above literature, this study hypothesizes that self-efficacy is positively related to employment intention, suggesting that unemployed youth with high self-efficacy will have higher employment intentions.

H2: Self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on employment intention

A research about the discussion of the relationship between learning motivation, training effectiveness, and job performance among employees in the high-tech industry, found that employees' motivation to participate in educational training, especially if driven by intrinsic motivation, leads to better behavioral performance in training effectiveness (Shahzadi, Javed, Pirzada, Nasreen, & Khanam, 2014). also explored the influence of training participation motivation on training effectiveness, finding that trainees' motivation significantly positively impacts their training effectiveness. Based on the above literature, this study hypothesizes that intrinsic training motivation is positively related to training effectiveness, leading to the hypothesis that unemployed youth with higher intrinsic motivation will have higher training effectiveness after participating in vocational training.

H3: Training motivation has a significant positive impact on training effectiveness.

Chen et al. (2021) pointed out that vocational training is crucial for a stable employment system, as it prepares individuals for employment, stabilizes jobs, and enhances or stimulates employment and reemployment intentions. Cullen et al. (2014) also found that learning motivation has a significant positive impact on employment intentions, particularly in the sub-dimensions of interest motivation and social motivation. This study hypothesizes that training motivation is positively related to employment intention, suggesting that unemployed youth with strong training motivation will have higher employment intentions.

H4: Training motivation has a significant positive impact on employment intention.

Vocational training aims to assist and enhance the employment skills of the unemployed, thereby promoting national employment (Switzer et al., 2005). Therefore, whether conducted by the central government, entrusted to private training institutions, or subsidized by local governments, the "employment rate" after training is considered

the most important indicator of vocational training effectiveness for the unemployed. According to the literature, training effectiveness positively impacts job performance, job satisfaction, and employee retention rates, highlighting the relationship between training and employment. Since this study focuses on unemployed youth who are not currently employed and who aspire to enter related industries in the future, the study links training effectiveness with employment intention. Based on the above literature, this study hypothesizes that training effectiveness is positively related to employment intention, suggesting that unemployed youth with high training effectiveness will have higher employment intentions.

H5: Training effectiveness has a significant positive impact on employment intention.

2. Method

This study adopts a quantitative research approach, distributing a wide-scale questionnaire to collect opinions from participants in vocational training programs. The objective is to investigate the impact of three major dimensions—self-efficacy, training motivation, and training effectiveness—on employment intentions.

The data collection process involves disseminating questionnaires to a broad audience of vocational training participants. The responses will provide valuable insights into the participants' perspectives and experiences regarding their self-efficacy, motivation for participating in the training, the effectiveness of the training, and their employment intentions. To analyze the collected data, this study employs regression analysis, utilizing statistical software. Regression analysis is particularly suitable for exploring the relationships between multiple independent variables (self-efficacy, training motivation, and training effectiveness) and a dependent variable (employment intention). By applying these statistical tools, the study aims to quantify the effects of self-efficacy, training motivation, and training effectiveness on the employment intentions of unemployed youth participating in vocational training programs.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of government measures in addressing youth unemployment. Among the six initiatives aimed at encouraging youth employment, the Taiwan government “The First Industrial Talents” training program specifically targets unemployed youth aged 15 to 29 by offering vocational training courses. This aligns with the age group experiencing the highest unemployment rates. Therefore, this study focuses on graduates of the “The First Industrial Talents” program as the primary research subjects.

Based on the outlined objectives, the study population has to meet the following criteria, one is unemployed youth aged 15 to 29, and the other one is participants who have completed the vocational training courses under the “The First Industrial Talents”. By focusing on these criteria, the study aims to accurately assess the impact of the “The First Industrial Talents” on improving employment outcomes for the most affected age group in the youth population.

The questionnaire for this study is based on the research framework and has been adjusted and refined following a review of relevant literature. The finalized questionnaire is divided into five major sections: self-efficacy scale to measure the self-efficacy of unemployed youth; training motivation scale to assess the motivations of participants attending the “The First Industrial Talents” programs; training effectiveness scale to evaluate the effectiveness of the training received during the program; employment intention scale to catch the employment intentions of participants after completing the course; and demographic information to collect basic personal data of the respondents. The questionnaire consists of 44 questions in total.

The research is conducted in two stages to ensure the reliability and validity of the study. A pretest Questionnaire was conducted firstly. Initially, a pretest questionnaire is designed to evaluate the feasibility, validity, and

completeness of the research tools. Feedback from respondents during the pretest phase is collected and analyzed. Based on this feedback, necessary adjustments, additions, or deletions are made to the questionnaire items to improve clarity and relevance. Then a full sample survey was conducted. After refining the questionnaire based on the pretest results, the finalized version is administered to the full sample of the study population. This step ensures that the data collected is comprehensive and reflective of the study's objectives. By following this structured process, the study aims to gather robust data to assess the impact of the "The First Industrial Talents" on the employment outcomes of unemployed youth.

In the preliminary testing phase, this study conducted an online small-sample test, collecting a total of 26 questionnaires. All 26 questionnaires were valid, resulting in a 100% effective response rate. The collected data underwent factor analysis, and items that did not meet statistical standards were removed.

Using the PLS (Partial Least Squares) path model, factor loadings were examined to support each dimension. Items with factor loadings below the threshold of 0.7 were deleted to ensure internal consistency and enhance the explanatory power of the indicators. A total of 14 items were deleted during this phase. After these deletions, a re-execution of statistical analysis confirmed that all factor loadings met the required standards. The revised questionnaire now better reflects the underlying constructs with improved internal consistency.

3. Results

This study distributed an online questionnaire. A total of 127 questionnaires were collected, with 6 incomplete responses excluded, resulting in 121 valid questionnaires. The effective response rate was 95.27%. All participants had experience attending Taiwan government "The First Industrial Talents" program.

In terms of gender distribution, the number of female participants slightly exceeded that of males, with 66 female participants making up 55% of the sample, while the remaining 55 participants were male, comprising 45% of the sample. Regarding age, the largest age group among participants was those aged 25-29 years, accounting for 49% of the sample with 59 participants. The second-largest group was those aged 20-24 years, representing 41% with 50 participants. The smallest age group was the 15-19 years cohort, with only 12 participants, making up 10% of the total.

When examining work experience, the majority of participants had less than one year of work experience, accounting for 31% of the sample. This was followed by recent graduates who had not yet entered the workforce, comprising 24% of the participants. Other categories of work experience were distributed as follows: 13% had 3-5 years of experience, 12% had 1-2 years of experience, and another 12% had 2-3 years of experience. Those with more than five years of work experience were the fewest, representing only 8% of the participants. This distribution suggests that most participants joined the vocational training program within a year after completing their highest level of education.

In terms of educational attainment, a significant majority of participants were university graduates, with 92 individuals holding a university degree, constituting 76% of the sample. The remaining participants were evenly split between those with a high school or vocational school/junior college education and those with postgraduate degrees, each group comprising 12% of the sample. Only one participant had a junior high school education, making up 1% of the total. These results provide a comprehensive overview of the demographic characteristics of the study's participants, highlighting a predominantly young, recently educated cohort with a significant portion having limited work experience.

Analysis of the Impact of Self-Efficacy, Training Motivation, and Training Effectiveness on Employment Intention

The statistical results supported Hypothesis H1: self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on educational training effectiveness ($\beta=0.227$, $T=3.522$, $P<0.001$). The analysis indicates that higher self-efficacy, or greater confidence in oneself, leads to higher training effectiveness after participating in vocational training. Therefore, Hypothesis H1 is supported by the data. The statistical results supported Hypothesis H2: self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on employment intention ($\beta=0.229$, $T=2.624$, $P<0.01$). The analysis reveals that higher self-efficacy, or greater confidence in one's learning outcomes, leads to higher employment intentions after completing vocational training. Thus, Hypothesis H2 is supported by the data. The statistical results supported Hypothesis H3: training motivation has a significant positive impact on training effectiveness ($\beta=0.751$, $T=14.427$, $P<0.001$). The analysis shows that higher training motivation, or a greater desire to gain from the course, leads to higher training effectiveness after participating in vocational training. Therefore, Hypothesis H3 is supported by the data. The statistical results did not support Hypothesis H4: training motivation did not have a significant positive impact on employment intention ($\beta=-0.149$, $T=1.007$, $P=0.314 > 0.05$). The analysis indicates that training motivation does not significantly influence the employment intentions of participants after completing the vocational training. Therefore, Hypothesis H4 is not supported by the data. The statistical results supported Hypothesis H5: training effectiveness has a significant positive impact on employment intention ($\beta=0.633$, $T=4.456$, $P<0.001$). The analysis reveals that higher training effectiveness, or greater gains from the course, leads to higher employment intentions after completing the training. Thus, Hypothesis H5 is supported by the data. These numbers are listed as following table:

Hypothesis	Structural Path	Standard Deviation	T-Value	P-Value	Result
H1	Self-Efficacy→Training Effectiveness	0.064	3.522	0.000	Supported
H2	Self-Efficacy→Employment Intention	0.087	2.624	0.009	Supported
H3	Training Motivation→Training Effectiveness	0.052	14.427	0.000	Supported
H4	Training Motivation→Employment Intention	0.148	1.007	0.314	Not Supported
H5	Training Effectiveness→Employment Intention	0.142	4.456	0.000	Supported

To explore whether the positive relationship between self-efficacy and employment intention is mediated by training effectiveness, a mediation effect analysis was conducted using hierarchical regression. In the first step, the coefficient of self-efficacy on employment intention was 0.444. In the second step, the coefficient of self-efficacy on employment intention decreased to 0.214 when training effectiveness was included in the model. This reduction indicates that the effect of self-efficacy on employment intention is partially mediated by training effectiveness. The significant values in the second model confirm that both self-efficacy and training effectiveness independently contribute to employment intention, but the influence of self-efficacy is diminished when accounting for the mediating effect of training effectiveness. This finding substantiates that training effectiveness plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between self-efficacy and employment intention. The statistical results are presented as following:

Model	B	Standard Error	β Value	T Value	Significance
1	(Constant)	2.307	0.331	6.961	0.000

	Self-Efficacy Mean	0.435	0.080	0.444	5.404	0.000
2	(Constant)	0.819	0.392		2.090	0.039
	Self-Efficacy Mean	0.210	0.081	0.214	2.578	0.011
	Training Effectiveness Mean	0.567	0.099	0.478	5.742	0.000

To determine whether gender influences the independent constructs in this study, an independent samples T-test was conducted to assess whether there are differences in the constructs based on gender. The analysis results indicate a significant difference in the self-efficacy construct based on gender. The T-test results show a T value of 2.425 and a P value of 0.017, which is less than the 0.05 threshold for significance. This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference in self-efficacy between males and females. The mean self-efficacy score for males was 4.22, while the mean self-efficacy score for females was 3.92. This indicates that, on average, males have higher self-efficacy compared to females.

Moreover, to understand whether the job-seeking experience of training participants affects any single construct in this study, an independent samples T-test was conducted, similar to the previous analysis on gender. This test evaluates whether there are differences in each construct based on job-seeking experience. The analysis results indicate that job-seeking experience has a significant impact on the employment intention construct. The T-test results show a T value of 3.222 and a P value of 0.002, which is less than the 0.05 threshold for significance. This suggests a statistically significant difference in employment intention between participants with job-seeking experience and those without. The mean employment intention score for participants with job-seeking experience was 4.21, while the mean score for those without job-seeking experience was 3.81. This indicates that participants who have previously attempted to seek employment generally have higher employment intentions compared to those who have not.

To thoroughly understand whether different age groups influence the independent constructs in this study, a one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was conducted to explore these relationships further. The F value on the employment intention is 4.780 with a P value of 0.010. Since the P value is less than 0.05, there is a significant effect of age on employment intention. There is a significant difference in employment intention between participants aged 15-19 and those aged 25-29. This finding suggests that older participants are generally more ready and willing to enter the workforce after completing vocational training compared to their younger counterparts.

4. Discussion

The hypothesis that self-efficacy positively influences training effectiveness was supported by the data. Individuals with high self-efficacy are confident in overcoming challenges and facing new tasks fearlessly. They are likely to complete assignments given by instructors successfully, signifying that they have internalized new knowledge from the course.

The hypothesis that self-efficacy positively influences employment intention was also supported. The primary goal of vocational training is to prepare participants for employment. Participants are usually those who have completed their education and are not currently employed, encouraging them to select courses related to their desired future careers. Therefore, the period of participating in vocational training often serves as a bridge between school and the workplace. Higher self-efficacy among trainees, even when facing challenges, leads to higher employment intentions.

The hypothesis that training motivation positively influences training effectiveness was supported. Participants with high training motivation are highly engaged in the courses they choose and are eager to gain knowledge from them. This high level of engagement leads to better absorption of new knowledge and higher training effectiveness.

For instance, a participant in the “E-commerce and Digital Marketing Talent Training Program” had a clear goal of learning how to operate social media and plan content, leading to strong learning motivation and excellent training outcomes.

The hypothesis that training motivation positively influences employment intention was not supported by the data. To understand this result, interviews were conducted with participants, revealing varied motivations for attending the courses. Some participants attended the courses out of interest or to learn additional skills, rather than with a direct intention of entering related industries. This diversity in motivations explains the lack of a significant impact on employment intentions.

The hypothesis that training effectiveness positively influences employment intention was supported. Participants who achieved high training effectiveness gained the necessary knowledge and skills for their chosen industry, boosting their confidence and willingness to seek employment in related fields. The “The First Industrial Talents” includes employment counseling courses, such as resume writing and interview skills, enhancing participants’ employability and supporting their job search efforts.

Moreover, four findings are demonstrated as following:

The analysis confirmed that training effectiveness partially mediates the positive impact of self-efficacy on employment intention. Even participants with high self-efficacy may experience reduced employment intentions if they encounter difficulties during the training that lower their training effectiveness. This mediation effect highlights the importance of training effectiveness in realizing the potential of self-efficacy.

Furthermore, the study found that male participants generally exhibited higher self-efficacy than female participants. This aligns with Bandura’s social learning theory, which posits that behavior is influenced by social environment, cognition, and behavior. In societies with traditional gender roles, such as Taiwan’s historically male-dominated society, males are often expected to be more competent, leading to higher self-efficacy.

Participants aged 25-29 showed higher employment intentions compared to those aged 15-19. This reflects the impact of Taiwan’s educational policies, where most students continue their education after junior high school, resulting in a lower number of unemployed youth in the 15-19 age group. Additionally, the low employment intention among this age group is due to their continued focus on education rather than immediate employment.

The study found no significant effects of gender and job-seeking experience on the hypothesis pathways, nor did work experience significantly impact any single construct. This may be due to the narrow age range of participants and the focus on pre-employment vocational training. Future research with a broader range of work experiences could further validate these findings.

The theoretical contributions are that previous studies on vocational training primarily focused on training needs, satisfaction, and effectiveness, rarely incorporating employment intention. By including employment intention in this study, we extend the research framework to understand the factors influencing post-training employment rates, providing a broader perspective on vocational training research.

The practical contributions are that the study findings suggest that self-efficacy enhances employment intentions. Therefore, future trainee selection processes could include self-efficacy assessments alongside pre-course evaluations of relevant knowledge. By understanding trainees’ self-efficacy, training motivation, and career aspirations, training programs can better select candidates who are likely to achieve high post-training employment rates, fulfilling the ultimate goal of vocational training initiatives.

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